

Research Software Engineer at the Netherlands eScience Center: Job Description

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Job descriptions

The job descriptions of the Netherlands eScience Center are of a generic character, meaning that they include key elements without mentioning the full list of tasks and activities. Personalized tasks can be discussed within the job performance cycle, as they can evolve over time and differ from year to year. All positions require a professional command of English. A job description focuses on responsibilities in order to address what the eScience Center aims to achieve.

eScience Research Software Engineer

To promote the use of eScience, and to initiate and develop digital methodologies, applications and high-quality software, based on research questions.

Job title	eScience Research Software Engineer, level 1 (scale 9)
Place in the organization	Reports to section head
Immediate contacts	Internal: section members, project team members and programme managers. External: project members, lead applicant
Purpose	To reuse and develop methodologies, applications and high-quality software based on well-defined instructions, with a view to answering concrete research questions and promoting the sustainable use of eScience technologies.
Main activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Guided by the expertise of colleagues, reuse or develop methodologies, applications and software that can be applied within a specific area of research.• Apply advanced software solutions based on research questions within a well-defined context.• Safeguard the quality of the eScience aspects within projects, including design, documentation and testing.• Provide user support for methodologies, software and applications developed by the eScience Center.• Contribute to the development (or reuse) of methodologies, software and applications.• Contribute to the publication of software and/or research.• Share knowledge with colleagues by giving presentations, co-organizing workshops, training courses and similar events.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Stay abreast of new developments in relevant fields.• Plan and manage work priorities to ensure deliverables and other deadlines are met.• Perform any other duties corresponding to the post.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Degree in higher education• Strong analytical skills• Demonstrable knowledge of the use of research-oriented digital methodologies• Practical knowledge of software engineering• Affinity with research
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on quality• Workmanship• Presenting• Cooperation• Result-oriented• Learning ability• Self-development

Job title	eScience Research Software Engineer, level 2 (scale 10)
Place in the organization	Reports to section head
Immediate contacts	Internal: section members, project team members and programme managers. External: project members, lead applicants, national and international eScience and RSE communities.
Purpose	To reuse and develop complex methodologies, applications and software of internationally recognized quality, based on general instructions, with a view to answering concrete research questions and promoting the sustainable use of eScience technologies.
Main activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translate research questions into solutions involving the effective application of advanced software engineering. • Independently develop and document methodologies, applications and software that can be applied to an academic discipline or find innovative ways to reuse existing software technologies. • Contribute to the timely reuse or development and application of eScience software solutions and methodologies, planning and managing work priorities to ensure deliverables and other deadlines are met. • Report on progress and results. • Safeguard the quality of the eScience components within projects, including design, documentation and testing. • Provide user support for methodologies, software and applications developed by the eScience Center. • Contribute to the publication of software and/or research. • Develop a professional profile through activities such as participation in conferences, hackathons and training events, membership of national and international eScience events, code reviewing, and involvement in national and international eScience initiatives. • Stay abreast of new developments in relevant fields. • Share knowledge internally and externally by giving presentations, workshops and training courses. • Show initiative in all areas. • Perform any other duties corresponding to the post.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD or equivalent

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Experience with research-oriented digital methodologies• Strong analytical skills• Knowledge of eScience technologies• Good software development skills and knowledge of software engineering• Affinity with academic research
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on quality• Workmanship• Research skills• Presenting• Cooperation• Need to achieve• Learning ability• Self-development

Job title	eScience Research Software Engineer, level 3 (scale 11)
Place in the organization	Reports to section head
Immediate contacts	Internal: section members, project team members and programme managers. External: project members, lead applicants, national and international eScience and RSE communities.
Purpose	To take a leading role in re-using and developing complex methodologies, applications and software of internationally recognized quality, with a view to answering complex research questions and promoting the sustainable use of eScience technologies.
Main activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translate complex research questions into solutions involving the effective application of advanced software engineering. • Independently develop and document methodologies, applications and software that can be applied to an academic discipline or find innovative ways to reuse existing software technologies. • Safeguard the timely development and application of eScience solutions, in line with project goals and deadlines. Plan and manage work priorities to ensure deliverables are met. Report on progress and results and advise on the direction of the project; and/or Pro-actively advise on the technical feasibility of projects within a technically complex environment. Take initiative to suggest and apply innovative technical solutions based on specialist technical expertise, to enhance project results. • Safeguard the quality of the eScience components within projects, including design, documentation and testing. • Provide user support for methodologies, software and applications developed by the eScience Center. • Seek opportunities to write and contribute to relevant software and/or research publications. Share these publications in a manner which enhances the visibility of the eScience Center. • Develop a professional profile through activities such as participation in conferences, hackathons and training events, membership of national and international eScience

	<p>events, code reviewing, and involvement in national and international eScience initiatives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Stay abreast of new developments in relevant fields.• Share knowledge internally and externally by giving presentations, workshops and training courses.• Show initiative in all areas.• Demonstrate independent performance in all areas.• Perform any other duties corresponding to the post.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• PhD or equivalent plus at least 2 years' experience demonstrating independently generated research outcomes within a research or commercial organization• Strong analytical skills• Demonstrated ability to take a leading role within research-oriented digital methodologies• Knowledge of eScience technologies• Excellent software development skills and knowledge of software architecture• Affinity with academic research
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on quality• Workmanship• Research skills• Presenting• Cooperation• Need to achieve• Networking• Self-development

Job title	Senior eScience Research Software Engineer, level 4 (scale 12)
Place in the organization	Reports to section head
Immediate contacts	Internal: section members, project team members and programme managers. External: project members, lead applicants, national and international eScience and RSE communities.
Purpose	Provide direction and leadership in re-using and developing complex methodologies, applications and software of internationally recognized quality, with a view to answering complex research questions and promoting the sustainable use of eScience technologies.
Main activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate leadership. • Translate complex research questions into solutions involving the effective application of advanced software engineering. • Independently develop and document ground-breaking methodologies, applications and software that can be applied to multiple academic disciplines and are internationally in the lead. • Ensure the timely development and application of eScience solutions, considering deadlines, goals, expected quality and predetermined costs. • Independently lead substantial research projects and/or develop (or coordinate the development of) methodologies, applications and software of a large, complex and specialized nature, and/or initiate the acquisition of external eScience projects. Effectively manage the relation with the main applicant. Report on progress and results and advise on the direction of the project; and/or Take the lead in bringing technical solutions to a higher level based on specialist technical expertise. Ensure technical feasibility of projects within a technically complex environment. Promote software sustainability beyond the boundaries of the particular project or domain. • Potentially co-supervise PhD-level RSEs. • Independently initiate and contribute to the publication of software and/or research. Share these publications in a manner which enhances the visibility of the eScience Center.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain a professional profile through activities such as participation in conferences, hackathons and training events, membership and leadership of national and international eScience events, code reviewing, and involvement in national and international eScience initiatives. • Stay abreast of new developments in relevant fields and initiate knowledge dissemination within and across sections. • Share knowledge internally and externally by giving presentations, contributing to workshops and training courses, and speaking at national and international conferences. • Show initiative in all areas. • Demonstrate independent performance in all areas. • Perform any other duties corresponding to the post.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD or equivalent plus 4 years' experience demonstrating independently generated research outcomes within a research or commercial organization • Strong analytical skills • Demonstrated leadership in developing research-oriented digital methodologies • Proven ability to independently manage research and/or software projects • Expert knowledge of eScience technologies • Excellent software development skills and knowledge of software architecture • Affinity with academic research
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on quality • Workmanship • Research skills • Cooperation • Leadership • Accountability • Networking • Independence

Job title	Senior eScience Research Software Engineer, level 5 (scale 13)
Place in the organization	Reports to section head
Immediate contacts	Internal: section members, project team members and programme managers. External: project members, lead applicants, national and international eScience and RSE communities.
Purpose	To substantially contribute to ground-breaking research engineering of the highest international standard. Provide direction and leadership in developing and re-using complex methodologies, applications and software of internationally recognized quality, with a view to answering complex research questions and promoting the sustainable use of eScience technologies. To translate organizational goals into project goals. To pioneer technological developments, promoting state-of-the-art solutions which increase the impact of the eScience Center on academic research.
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To acquire substantial external funding for projects applying eScience technologies to research questions, including the independent submission of full-fledged project plans, participating actively in research consortia, and leading research projects of a large and complex nature; or To independently develop (or coordinate the development of) methodologies, applications and software of a deeply complex and highly specialized nature that can be applied within multiple academic disciplines and are demonstrably at the international forefront of research software engineering. • Plan and manage work priorities to ensure deliverables and other deadlines are met. • Show initiative in all areas. • Demonstrate independent performance in all areas. • Perform any other duties corresponding to the post.
Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PhD or equivalent 4-6 years' experience demonstrating independently generated research outcomes within a research or commercial organization • Strong analytical skills • Demonstrated leadership within research-oriented digital methodologies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Proven ability to independently manage research and/or software projects• Expert knowledge of eScience technologies• Excellent software development skills and knowledge of software architecture• Affinity with academic research• Successful track record in independently attracting substantial research subsidies from external funding agencies, and/or• Demonstrable ability to go well beyond the state of the art in technology
Competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Focus on quality• Workmanship• Research skills• Cooperation• Leadership• Accountability• Networking• Independence

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